

ISSN 1759-0116 (Online)

ZooNova

Occasional Papers in Zoology

Number 49, Pages 1 – 2

**A replacement name for *Alienus* Peñaherrera-R., Sherwood,
León-E., Ríos-Tamayo & Drolshagen, 2025
(Araneae: Paratropididae)**

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Published on-line at zoonova.afriherp.org

Afriherp Communications, Greenford, United Kingdom

Date of publication: 30 April 2026

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lsid:zoobank.org:pub:969336AE-D255-4F22-9B22-61A76C35BE08

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Abstract

A replacement name is given for *Alienus* Penaherrera-R., Sherwood, León-E., Ríos-Tamayo & Drolshagen, 2025 which is preoccupied by *Alienus* Galileo & Martins, 2010 (Coleoptera).

Key words: homonym, nomenclature, spider

Introduction

Peñaherrera-R. *et al.* (2025) published the first modern morphological phylogeny of the family Paratropididae Simon, 1889, describing three new genera and 11 new species. It has recently come to our attention (Theo Blick pers. comm.) that one genus name, *Alienus* Penaherrera-R., Sherwood, León-E., Ríos-Tamayo & Drolshagen, 2025 is preoccupied in the Coleoptera by *Alienus* Galileo & Martins, 2010. In this work, we provide a replacement name, as required by the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (1999).

Taxonomy

***Allpanuna* nom. nov.**

Alienus Peñaherrera -R., Sherwood, León-E., Ríos-Tamayo & Drolshagen, 2025: 686 (preoccupied in Coleoptera by *Alienus* Galileo & Martins, 2010: 388)

Type species: Allpanuna pollex comb. nov.

Etymology: The generic epithet is derived from the Quechua words *allpa* meaning soil, and *nuna* meaning spirit. The name refers to the behaviour of these spiders, which cover their entire body with soil particles, blending with the substrate and appearing as a spirit emerging from the soil. The gender is feminine.

Species included:

Allpanuna abdita (Peñaherrera-R., Sherwood, Ríos-Tamayo & Drolshagen, 2025) **comb. nov.**,

Allpanuna alo (Peñaherrera-R., Sherwood, León-E, Ríos-Tamayo & Drolshagen, 2025) **comb. nov.**,

Allpanuna awa (Sherwood, Brescovit & Lucas, 2023) **comb. nov.**,

Allpanuna basho (Sherwood, Drolshagen, Peñaherrera-R. & Ríos-Tamayo, 2025) **comb. nov.**,

Allpanuna crocea (Peñaherrera-R., Sherwood, Ríos-Tamayo & Drolshagen, 2025) **comb. nov.**,

Allpanuna paschoa (Dupérré & Tapia, 2024) **comb. nov.**,

Allpanuna pollex (Peñaherrera-R., Sherwood, León-E, Ríos-Tamayo & Drolshagen, 2025) **comb. nov.**,

Allpanuna roigi (Ríos-Tamayo, Sherwood, Peñaherrera-R., León-E. & Drolshagen, 2025) **comb. nov.**

Acknowledgements

We warmly thank Theo Blick (World Spider Catalog) for alerting us to our error.

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Submitted: 7 Jan 2026

Accepted: 14 March 2026